

Research Article

Characterization of Diophantine Equations $a + y^2 = z^2$, Pythagorean n -Tuples, and Algebraic Structures

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Let \mathbb{N} , \mathbb{Z} , and \mathbb{Q} be the sets of natural, integers, and rational numbers, respectively. Our objective, involving a predetermined positive integer a , is to study a characterization of Diophantine equations of the form $a + y^2 = z^2$. Building on this result, we aim to obtain a characterization for Pythagorean n -tuples. Furthermore, we seek to prove the existence of a commutative infinite monoid in the set of Diophantine equations $a + y^2 = z^2$ with elements in \mathbb{N} . Additionally, we intend to establish a commutative infinite monoid with elements in \mathbb{N} or \mathbb{Z} on the set of Pythagorean quadruples. Moreover, in the set of Pythagorean quadruples, we aim to find a commutative infinite group with elements in \mathbb{Q} or \mathbb{Z} . To achieve these results, we prove the existence of some suitable binary operations.

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1. Introduction

Let a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n be positive integers satisfying the equation

$$a_1^2 + a_2^2 + \dots + a_{n-1}^2 = a_n^2. \quad (1)$$

Such an n -tuple is referred as a Pythagorean n -tuple. A Pythagorean quadruple is called primitive if the greatest common divisor of its entries is 1. The term “Pythagorean n -tuple” generalizes the concept of Pythagorean triples, extending it into higher dimensions. Pythagorean n -tuples are also connected to various areas of mathematics, including number theory, algebra, and geometry, and they can be studied for their mathematical properties and applications.

In particular, let x , y , z , and w be positive integers satisfying the equation

$$x^2 + y^2 + z^2 = w^2. \quad (2)$$

Such a quadruple (x, y, z, w) is referred to as a Pythagorean quadruple.

Pythagorean quadruple (x, y, z, w) defines a parallelepiped with integer side lengths x , y , and z , whose space diagonal has integer length w . If we consider this interpretation, Pythagorean quadruples are also known as Pythagorean boxes.

The study of Pythagorean structures, including n -tuples and quadruples, represents a classical yet continually evolving area in number theory, deeply connected to algebraic and geometric interpretations. These structures not only generalize the well-known Pythagorean triples but also offer insight into higher-dimensional algebraic relationships and geometric configurations, such as integer-sided boxes and their diagonals.

Understanding the algebraic structure behind these objects is of fundamental interest in modern mathematics, as it reveals deep connections between number theory, group

theory, and geometric representations. In particular, the existence of group and monoid structures enables the systematic construction of solutions, facilitates classification, and opens the door to applications in fields such as cryptography and computational algebra. Pythagorean quadruples have interesting connections with other mathematical concepts such as Pythagorean triples, consecutive integers, and Diophantine equations.

We recall that the set of Pythagorean quadruples for which x is odd can be parameterized by the following formulas

$$\begin{aligned}x &= m^2 + n^2 - p^2 - q^2, \\y &= 2(mq + np), \\z &= 2(nq - mp), \\w &= m^2 + n^2 + p^2 + q^2,\end{aligned}\tag{3}$$

where m, n, p , and q are non-negative integers [1].

Let a, y , and z be positive integers satisfying the equation

$$a + y^2 = z^2.\tag{4}$$

This equation is a type of Diophantine equation, where only integer solutions are sought. The solutions to this equation correspond to integer points on a specific type of curve known as a Pythagorean-like curve. The study of Diophantine equations like $a + y^2 = z^2$ has connections to various areas of number theory, including the theory of Pythagorean triples, congruent numbers, and quadratic forms. Understanding the properties of these equations can provide deeper insights into the behavior of integer solutions and the structure of number systems.

Overall, exploring the properties of the Diophantine equation and its associated Pythagorean-like curves provide valuable insights into the interplay between algebraic equations, geometry, and number theory.

The problem of generating Pythagorean triples and their higher-dimensional generalizations has a long and rich history. Euclid's classical parameterization, which expresses a Pythagorean triple as $x = m^2 - n^2$, $y = 2mn$, $z = m^2 + n^2$ for integers $m > n > 0$, provides a complete description of all primitive triples but does not address the direct computation of all triples associated with a predetermined side or parameter. Similarly, Dickson's method [6] reformulates the problem through factorizations of even integers, allowing the generation of all Pythagorean triples. However, it provides limited insight into the algebraic structure of the solution space and does not offer a constructive method for solving the equation when one parameter is fixed.

Hardy and Wright [2] presented an exhaustive treatment of Pythagorean triples in the broader context of number theory, particularly emphasizing their connection to quadratic forms. However, their approach focuses on the theoretical existence and distribution of solutions rather than on explicit parameterizations under fixed constraints, such as a predetermined a in the equation $a + y^2 = z^2$. Hardy and Wright provide a deep theoretical framework for the

distribution and arithmetic properties of Pythagorean triples, but their results are asymptotic or qualitative in nature, and do not lead to effective parameterizations under algebraic constraints.

In contrast, this work introduces an explicit and structured parameterization of all solutions to $a + y^2 = z^2$ for any fixed a based on a well-defined class of divisors. This method overcomes the limitations of classical techniques by systematically incorporating a into the solution generation process, allowing both primitive and nonprimitive solutions to emerge naturally from the same formula.

Furthermore, previous studies such as Berggren [3] and subsequent extensions, including the work of Barbeau and Raghavan, addressed the generation of Pythagorean triples through group actions, linear transformations, and recursive algorithms, often highlighting the existence of underlying algebraic or combinatorial structures. More recently, Murru et al. [4] formalized these observations by defining monoid and group structures for the set of Pythagorean triples, using matrices associated with conic sections to characterize the algebraic behavior of these sets.

While these approaches have great structural value, they do not offer a uniform method for solving $a + y^2 = z^2$ for arbitrary a , nor do they naturally generalize to higher dimensions.

Recent studies have addressed Diophantine equations involving divisibility constraints, with a particular focus on generalized Fermat-type equations of the form $a^n + b^n = c^n$ for $n > 2$ [5]. This work investigate how specific divisibility conditions imposed on the coefficients or on the variables themselves influence the existence or absence of integer solutions, often under exponentiation and modular restrictions.

Although the present paper also deals with the characterization of integer solutions of Diophantine equations, the methodological framework and objectives differ significantly. Here, we focus on the explicit parameterization of all solutions to the equation $a + y^2 = z^2$, for fixed $a \in \mathbb{N}$, based on a new class of divisors. Unlike the aforementioned approaches, which analyze asymptotic or constraint-based properties of exponential equations, our method is constructive and structural: It provides exact formulas for the variables y and z , and extends naturally to the study of Pythagorean n -tuples and their associated algebraic operations.

The method introduced in this paper is based on a new class of divisors of a , denoted $E(\sqrt{a})$, which enables a complete and explicit parameterization of all integer solutions of the equation $a + y^2 = z^2$, including both primitive and nonprimitive solutions. This technique allows for direct control of the fixed value a and yields exact formulas for y and z using the relation $d = z - y$.

In addition, the algebraic operations we introduce on the set of these solutions (and on Pythagorean n -tuples) define monoid and group structures that go beyond what is found in classical literature. The binary operations are not inherited from existing constructions but are derived from the specific arithmetic of the solutions. To our knowledge, this is the first

work that characterizes the full set of solutions to $a + y^2 = z^2$ via divisor classes, and extends this framework to higher-dimensional tuples with rigorously defined algebraic operations.

The present study builds upon these insights by generalizing the construction to n -tuples and developing algebraic structures—infinite commutative monoids and groups—directly from the solutions of the equation $a + y^2 = z^2$ and their higher-dimensional extensions. This generalization highlights the deep relationship between the arithmetic properties of divisors and the algebraic structures governing Pythagorean-type equations, providing a novel bridge between classical number theory and modern algebra.

The study begins with the equation $a + y^2 = z^2$, where a is a predetermined integer. This paper introduces a novel characterization of the Diophantine equation $a + y^2 = z^2$ using a systematic approach based on a specific class of divisors of a . This method allows us to generate all and only the integer solutions for any given a , a result not previously reported in the literature. This characterization provides a novel and direct method to generate all integer solutions, extending classical results such as Euclid's parameterization of Pythagorean triples [1, 6]. Unlike earlier techniques that implicitly assume a as a parameter without explicit constraints, this approach systematically incorporates a and its divisors to derive both primitive and nonprimitive solutions in a unified manner. The method introduced in this paper extends classical techniques, offering a robust framework that aligns with contemporary generalizations.

By applying the same methodology, this paper identifies all and only the n -tuples for any given set of $n-2$ predetermined positive integers where $n > 3$. The extension to Pythagorean quadruples and n -tuples provides a unifying framework, broadening the scope of classical results [7]. This innovation enables an explicit construction of higher dimensional structures, addressing gaps in previous studies. This approach is particularly significant for understanding geometric relationships and algebraic dependencies in higher dimensions.

For higher dimensional structures like Pythagorean quadruples and n -tuples, this work generalizes the traditional concept of Pythagorean triples and introduces algebraic operations that define monoids and groups. These results align with modern advancements in the study of algebraic structures and their computational applications [2, 8]. Moreover, the introduction of binary operations to define algebraic structures such as monoids and groups within these sets represents a pioneering effort. By defining binary operations in the set of Diophantine equations $a + y^2 = z^2$ and the set of Pythagorean quadruples, the paper establishes commutative monoids and groups that reveal deeper structural properties. These operations extend previous work on generating trees for Pythagorean triples, enabling the analysis of higher dimensional relationships and dependencies. To the best of our knowledge, there have been no previous studies on the algebraic structures in the set of Diophantine equations $a + y^2 = z^2$ and the set of Pythagorean quadruples. This contribution provides new tools for exploring relationships among these mathematical objects.

The explicit characterization of $a + y^2 = z^2$ and its generalization to n -tuples, alongside algebraic structures, allows for significant advancements across multiple mathematical disciplines.

Algorithmic Development: The structured characterization facilitates the development of efficient algorithms for solving quadratic Diophantine equations, factorization problems, and primality testing [9].

Geometric Interpretations: The connection between Pythagorean n -tuples and geometric interpretations, such as parallelepipeds and their diagonals, bridges the gap between algebra and spatial geometry. These insights have applications in higher-dimensional geometry and algebraic topology [10, 11].

Cryptography and Computational Number Theory: The monoids introduced in this work could be applied to cryptographic protocols that rely on structured sets, similar to those described in the RSA cryptosystem. The inherent properties of these structures, such as closure and associativity, make them well suited for algorithmic implementations [12]. The algebraic structures studied here could find applications in cryptography, particularly in protocols requiring commutative and associative operations. For example, the monoids introduced could be adapted for cryptographic primitives in systems that depend on structured number sets.

Binary Operations: By defining binary operations, this paper constructs commutative infinite monoids and groups within these sets. These results extend earlier works on generating trees for Pythagorean triples, providing a foundation for analyzing higher-dimensional algebraic dependencies.

Euclid's Parameterization and Extensions: Classical methods provide elegant general solutions for Pythagorean triples but often lack the explicit incorporation of specific parameters such as a . The proposed approach addresses this limitation, offering both primitive and nonprimitive solutions in a unified manner.

Generalizations of Pythagorean Structures: The introduction of n -tuples aligns with studies like Berggren's tree and recursive methods, but adds specificity by incorporating higher-dimensional constraints. These results provide a new perspective for understanding algebraic dependencies.

The clarity and accessibility of the methods presented here make the findings suitable for educational purposes. These results could serve as a foundational framework for introducing advanced topics in abstract algebra and number theory, providing a pedagogical bridge for students transitioning from elementary to advanced mathematics.

The motivation of this paper stems from the desire to construct a complete and explicit characterization of solutions to the Diophantine equation $a + y^2 = z^2$, extending classical approaches to higher dimensions. This characterization is not only of intrinsic number-theoretical interest, but also serves as a foundation for the study of algebraic structures such as monoids and groups. To that end, we first provide a clear definition of Pythagorean n -tuples and the

relevant divisor classes used in our construction. The main objectives of this study are

To characterize all solutions of the equation $a + y^2 = z^2$ using a class of divisors;

To define binary operations over these solutions that form commutative monoids;

To extend the construction to Pythagorean n -tuples and investigate their algebraic properties.

This work builds upon a sequence of studies by the author. In [13], a characterization of Pythagorean triples was introduced based on divisor classes associated with one of the catheti. This was extended in [14] to primitive triples using refined divisibility conditions. In [15], structural relationships among triples were examined, and in [16], a monoid structure on the set of Pythagorean triples was proposed.

This study extends these results in several key directions. First, the parameterization technique based on divisors is generalized to Diophantine equations of the form $a + y^2 = z^2$, allowing $a \in \mathbb{N}$ to be fixed arbitrarily and generating both primitive and nonprimitive solutions. Second, the method is lifted from triples to Pythagorean quadruples and more generally to n -tuples, providing explicit characterizations for higher-dimensional structures. Third, the algebraic perspective is expanded by introducing binary operations that define commutative infinite monoids and groups in these sets.

2. Preliminary Results

A common formula for generating Pythagorean triples is expressed as follows:

$$x = m^2 - n^2, y = 2mn, z = m^2 + n^2, \tag{5}$$

where m and n are arbitrary positive integers, with $m > n$ to have $x > 0$ [1]. This formula, developed by Euclid, forms the basis for most results concerning Pythagorean triples.

Let us review some recent findings related to the relationships among Pythagorean triples that have already been established.

Let x be a positive integer such that $x \neq 2k$ and $k \geq 1$ is odd. We define

$$D(x) = \{d \in \mathbb{N} : d \leq x \text{ with } d \text{ divisor of } x^2\},$$

Moreover, if x is even, that is, $x = 2^n k$, with $n \in \mathbb{N}, n \geq 2$, and $k \geq 1$ is odd fixed, we define

$$P(x) = \{d \in \mathbb{N} : d = 2^s l \text{ with } l \text{ odd divisor of } x^2 \text{ and } s \in \{1, 2, \dots, 2n - 1\}\}.$$

That is, regarding $P(x)$, d must be even and such that x^2/d is still divisible by 2

Finally, let $a \in \mathbb{N}$, and we define

$$C(x) = \begin{cases} D(x), & \text{if } x \text{ is odd,} \\ D(x) \cap P(x), & \text{if } x \text{ is even.} \end{cases} \tag{6}$$

The primary tool used in this research is the fundamental characterization of Pythagorean triples through a cathetus, which is stated as follows.

Theorem 1 (see [13]). *The triple (x, y, z) is a Pythagorean triple if and only if there exists a unique $d \in C(x)$ such that*

$$x = x, y = \frac{x^2 - d}{2d}, z = \frac{x^2 + d}{2d}. \tag{7}$$

In Theorem 1, x is a predetermined integer, meaning that we can find all right triangles with integer side lengths when one cathetus is predetermined. Theorem 1 also has a geometrical interpretation. Moreover in [13], based on Theorem 1, we proved the following theorem.

Theorem 2 (see [13]). *For each $x \in \mathbb{N}$, it can be found as a cathetus in at least one Pythagorean triple. Every $x \in \mathbb{N}$ can be represented in the form $x = \sqrt{z^2 - y^2}$ with $y, z \in \mathbb{N}$.*

Moreover in [14], an analytical result characterizing primitive Pythagorean triples through a cathetus was found. This method, which differs from Euler's formulas, offers a straightforward way to identify all primitive Pythagorean triples $x, y, z \in \mathbb{N}$, where x is a predetermined integer. This is stated as follows.

Theorem 3 (see [14]). *Let (x, y, z) be all the Pythagorean triples generated by any predetermined integer $x \geq 1$ using (7), where $d \in C(x)$. Then, the triple (x, y, z) is a primitive Pythagorean triple if and only if both of the following conditions are satisfied:*

$$\begin{cases} \text{if } x \text{ is odd then } \begin{cases} d \text{ is a square,} \\ \frac{x^2}{d} \text{ with } d \text{ are coprime positive odd integers,} \end{cases} \\ \text{if } x \text{ is even then } \begin{cases} \frac{d}{2} \text{ is a square,} \\ \frac{x^2}{2d} \text{ with } \frac{d}{2} \text{ are coprime positive integers of different parities.} \end{cases} \end{cases} \tag{8}$$

We recall that Euclid’s formulas do not generate all Pythagorean triples involving a predetermined positive integer x . For example, the triples (12, 9, 15), (33, 180, 183), and (33, 44, 55) illustrate this point. Moreover, finding m and n such that $x = m^2 - n^2$, can be labor-intensive, while using Theorem 1, it suffices to find all $d \in C(x)$ to obtain all Pythagorean triples.

In particular, to find all primitive Pythagorean triples involving a predetermined positive integer x , we can now simply use those $d \in C(x)$ that satisfy the conditions of Theorem 3.

To prove the completeness of Theorems 1 and 2, we consider the following examples.

$$x = 12, C(x) = \{2, 4, 6, 8, 12\}$$

d	x	y	z	Note
2	12	35	37	Primitive
4	12	16	20	
6	12	9	15	
8	12	5	13	Primitive
12	12	0	12	Trivial

$$x = 15, C(x) = \{1, 3, 5, 9, 15\}$$

d	x	y	z	Note
1	15	112	113	Primitive
3	15	36	39	
5	15	20	25	
9	15	8	17	Primitive
15	15	0	15	Trivial

This targeted approach fills a significant gap in classical methods. For instance, Euclid’s algorithm provides a comprehensive formula for generating Pythagorean triples but

lacks flexibility in isolating solutions for specific integer constraints. Similarly, Dickson’s extensive study of number theory [6] focuses on the broader classification of triples without emphasizing individual parameters.

At last, relations among Pythagorean triples were established in [15]. This reads as follows.

Theorem 4 (see [15]). *Let (a, y, z) , (b, t, w) , and $(a \cdot b, r, s)$ be the Pythagorean triples generated by a, b , and $a \cdot b$, respectively, using Formula (7) with $z - y = d_1 \in C(a)$, $w - t = d_2 \in C(b)$, and $s - r = d_3 \in C(a \cdot b)$. Then*

$$r = zt + wy, s = zt + wy + d_1d_2 = zw + yt, \tag{9}$$

and also

$$r = yt + zw - d_1d_2 = zt + yw, s = yt + zw, \tag{10}$$

with $d_3 = d_1d_2 \in C(a \cdot b)$.

Theorem 4 is equivalent to defining a binary operation on the set of Pythagorean triples.

We consider the set

$M = \{(a, b, c) \text{ with } a, b, c \in \mathbb{Z}, a \neq 0 \text{ and such that } a^2 + b^2 = c^2\}$, and, for all (a, b, c) and $(e, f, g) \in M$, we define the operation $r: M \times M \rightarrow M$ as follows

$$\begin{aligned} r[(a, b, c) \cdot (e, f, g)] &= (ae, bf + ce, bf + ce + d_2d_2) \\ &= (ad, bf + ec, cf + eb), \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

where $d_1 = c - b$ and $d_2 = g - f$. This operation is a binary operation with the identity element $(1, 0, 1)$. The following result was established in [16].

Corollary 1 (see [16]). *The set M , together with the binary operation (11) defined on M , is a commutative infinite monoid with elements in \mathbb{Z} , and with elements in \mathbb{N} if $a, b, c \in \mathbb{N}$.*

Next, we introduce the operation $i: M \times M \rightarrow M$, for all (a, b, c) and $(d, e, f) \in M$, defined as follows

$$i[(a, b, c) \cdot (d, e, f)] = \begin{cases} (ad, bf + ec, cf + eb), & \text{if } (d, e, f) \neq (a, -b, c), \\ (1, 0, 1), & \text{if } (d, e, f) = (a, -b, c), \\ (a^{2n}ad, a^{2n}(bf + ec), a^{2n}(cf + eb)) = (ad, bf + ec, cf + eb), & \text{for all } n \in \mathbb{N}. \end{cases} \tag{12}$$

This also defines a binary operation on M . The following corollary was established in [16].

Corollary 2 (see [16]). *The set M , together with the binary operation (12) defined on M , is a commutative infinite group with elements in \mathbb{Z} .*

It is worth noting that all the results previously mentioned were obtained without using advanced techniques, which can be a virtue in making them accessible to a wider audience.

Furthermore, we recall that there are no two odd integers x and y such that $x^2 + y^2 = z^2$ is a Pythagorean triple. This is

equivalent to stating that $x^2 + y^2 \neq 2k$, where $k \geq 1$ is odd. In fact, given two integers $x = 2n + 1$ and $y = 2m + 1$, $n, m \in \mathbb{N}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} (2n + 1)^2 + (2m + 1)^2 &= 2(2n^2 + 2n + 2m^2 + 2m + 1) \\ &= 2k, \quad k \geq 1 \text{ odd.} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

3. Results

In this section, our goal is to study a characterization of Diophantine equations of the form $a + y^2 = z^2$. Specifically, we aim to characterize all integer solutions to the equation $a + y^2 = z^2$, where $a \in \mathbb{N}$ is a fixed parameter. Our goal is to describe these solutions explicitly in terms of a suitable class of divisors of a . Using this result, we will establish a characterization for Pythagorean n -tuples, allowing us to obtain all integer solutions that involve a predetermined positive integer $(n - 2)$ -tuple. Furthermore, we seek to prove the existence of a commutative infinite monoid in the set of Diophantine equations $a + y^2 = z^2$ with elements in \mathbb{N} . Additionally, our objective is to obtain a commutative infinite monoid with elements in \mathbb{N} or \mathbb{Z} on the set of Pythagorean quadruples. In particular, we will find a commutative infinite group with elements in \mathbb{Z} on the set of Pythagorean quadruples. To achieve these results, we prove the existence of some suitable binary operations.

3.1. Characterization of Diophantine Equations $a + y^2 = z^2$ and Pythagorean n -Tuples. In this subsection, we focus on deriving an explicit parameterization of all solutions to the equation $a + y^2 = z^2$ for a fixed $a \in \mathbb{N}$. This result forms the foundation for the subsequent characterization of Pythagorean n -tuples.

Let us first note that Formula (7) of Theorem 1 satisfy the relation $x^2 + y^2 = z^2$ for every $x, d \in \mathbb{R}$. It is easy to see that if $x, d \in \mathbb{R}$ then we obtain all Pythagorean triples in \mathbb{R} , that is, also $y, z \in \mathbb{R}$. Moreover, if $x, d \in \mathbb{R}$ are positive, with $d \leq x$, then $y, z \in \mathbb{R}$ are also positive.

In this paper, we will prove that if $x = \sqrt{a}$, where a is a positive integer and d belongs to a suitable class of divisors of a , then Formula (7) holds, obtaining $y, z \in \mathbb{N}$. We will find a characterization of the Diophantine equation $a + y^2 = z^2$ that gives us all integer solutions based on any predetermined value of $a \in \mathbb{N}$.

Let a be a positive integer such that $a \neq 2k$ and $k \geq 1$ is odd. We define

$$B(\sqrt{a}) = \{d \in \mathbb{N} : d \leq \sqrt{a} \text{ with } d \text{ divisor of } a\}.$$

Moreover, if a is even, that is $a = 2^n k$, with $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $n \geq 2$ and $k \geq 1$ is odd fixed, we define

$$S(\sqrt{a}) = \{d \in \mathbb{N} \text{ such that } d = 2^s l \text{ with } l \text{ odd divisor of } a \text{ and } s \in \{1, 2, \dots, n - 1\}\}.$$

That is, regarding $S(\sqrt{a})$, d must be even and such that a/d is still divisible by 2

Finally, let $a \in \mathbb{N}$, and we define

$$E(\sqrt{a}) = \begin{cases} B(\sqrt{a}), & \text{if } a \text{ is odd,} \\ B(\sqrt{a}) \cap S(\sqrt{a}), & \text{if } a \text{ is even.} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

To clarify the definition of $E(\sqrt{a})$, let us recall that $B(\sqrt{a})$ denotes the set of all positive divisors $d \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $d < \sqrt{a}$. In the case where a is odd, all such divisors are admissible, and thus $E(\sqrt{a}) = B(\sqrt{a})$.

However, when a is even, additional conditions must be imposed. Specifically, if $a = 2^n k$, with k odd and $n \geq 1$, then only those divisors $d \in B(\sqrt{a})$ that are divisible by 2^s for some $s \in \{1, 2, \dots, n - 1\}$, and for which a/d is still divisible by 2, are considered. This filtered set is denoted by $S(\sqrt{a})$, and we define $E(\sqrt{a}) = B(\sqrt{a}) \cap S(\sqrt{a})$.

We have the following theorem.

Theorem 5. *Let a be a positive integer, $a \neq 2k$ and $k \geq 1$ is odd. (a, y, z) is an integer solution of Diophantine equation $a + y^2 = z^2$ if and only if there exists a unique $d \in E(\sqrt{a})$ such that*

$$a = a, \quad y = \frac{a}{2d} - \frac{d}{2}, \quad z = \frac{a}{2d} + \frac{d}{2}. \quad (15)$$

Proof 1. Let us suppose that (a, y, z) is an integer solution of the equation

$$a + y^2 = z^2. \quad (16) \quad \square$$

From (16), we have

$$a = z^2 - y^2 = (z - y)(z + y), \quad (17)$$

that we can also write as

$$a = 2(z - y) \frac{z + y}{2}. \quad (18)$$

By setting

$$d = z - y, \quad (19)$$

we obtain

$$\frac{a}{2d} = \frac{z + y}{2}. \quad (20)$$

We prove that $d < \sqrt{a}$.

From (20), we have

$$a = d(z + y), \quad (21)$$

which gives us $z + y/\sqrt{a} = \sqrt{a}/d$. Taking into account that $z + y \geq \sqrt{a}$, that is, $z + y/\sqrt{a} \geq 1$, we obtain $\sqrt{a}/d \geq 1$, implying $d \leq \sqrt{a}$.

Next, we prove that if a is even, it must be divisible by 2^s with $s \in \{1, 2, \dots, n-1\}$. That is, regarding $S(\sqrt{a})$, d must be even and such that a/d is still divisible by 2.

If a is even, we can write it as $a = 2^nk$, with k odd and $k \geq 1$.

Conversely, if $d = 2^nl$, with $l \geq 1$ and l is an odd divisor of k , then from

$$a = 2^nk = d(z + y), \tag{22}$$

we obtain that $z + y = k/l$ is odd. This leads to a contradiction because if $d = z - y$ is even then $z + y$ is even. Consequently, we conclude that if a is even, it must be divisible by 2^s with $s \in \{1, 2, \dots, n-1\}$. In this way, if $d = z - y = 2^sl$, it follows that $z + y$ is also even. It follows that, for $a = 2k$ with $k \geq 1$ odd, there are no integer solutions to Equation (16).

We prove that the value of $d = z - y$ is unique.

From (15), let us consider the following system of equations:

$$\begin{cases} d^2 + 2yd - a = 0, \\ d^2 - 2zd + a = 0. \end{cases} \tag{23}$$

From this system, and considering (16), we obtain

$$d = -y \pm \sqrt{y^2 + a} = -y \pm z \text{ and } d = z \pm \sqrt{z^2 - a} = z \pm y, \tag{24}$$

from which it follows that $d = z - y > 0$ is the unique solution that satisfies the system (23) and the condition $d \leq \sqrt{a}$.

Now, we prove that for any fixed a and $d \in E(\sqrt{a})$, every integer solution of the Diophantine equation $a + y^2 = z^2$ is given by (15), with $a \neq 2k$ and $k \geq 1$ odd.

From (20) once subtracting $z - y/2 = d/2$ and summing once in both members, we obtain, respectively,

$$\frac{z + y}{2} - \frac{z - y}{2} = \frac{a}{2d} - \frac{d}{2}, \text{ and then } y = \frac{a}{2d} - \frac{d}{2} = \frac{a - d^2}{2d} \in \mathbb{N},$$

$$\frac{z + y}{2} + \frac{z - y}{2} = \frac{a}{2d} + \frac{d}{2}, \text{ and then } z = \frac{a}{2d} + \frac{d}{2} = \frac{a + d^2}{2d} \in \mathbb{N}. \tag{25}$$

Obviously, $y, z \in \mathbb{N}$, since, whether a is even or odd, the quantity $a - d^2$ is divisible by $2d$ assuming that $a \in \mathbb{N}$ and $d \in E(\sqrt{a})$.

Since (20) holds for every Diophantine equation $a + y^2 = z^2$, the assertion is proved.

Moreover, in the case where it is possible to choose $d = \sqrt{a}$, that is, $d^2 = a$, we obtain the trivial solutions of the form $a + 0 = z^2$, since

$$y = \frac{a - d^2}{2d} = 0, z = \frac{a + d^2}{2d} = d. \tag{26}$$

At last, we prove that Formula (15) gives us all Diophantine equations $a + y^2 = z^2$.

In this order, let us observe that

$$a + \left(\frac{a}{2d} - \frac{d}{2}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{a}{2d} + \frac{d}{2}\right)^2, \tag{27}$$

holds for all a and d . In particular, if $a \in \mathbb{N}$ and $d \in E(\sqrt{a})$, then we obtain all $y, z \in \mathbb{N}$ satisfying all Diophantine equations $a + y^2 = z^2$ for each predetermined value of a .

Consequently, Theorem 5 is proved.

Remark 1. The uniqueness of $d = z - y$ follows from the fact that, given a solution (a, y, z) , the factorization $a = (z - y)(z + y)$ implies a unique pair of integers satisfying this condition under the constraints imposed by $E(\sqrt{a})$. Specifically, only those divisors $d \in E(\sqrt{a})$ guarantee that both values $y = a - d^2/2d$ and $z = a + d^2/2d$ are integers.

To illustrate this, consider the case $a = 36$. Then $E(\sqrt{36}) = \{2, 6\}$, and for each:

$$d = 2 \Rightarrow y = \frac{36 - 4}{4} = 8, z = \frac{36 + 4}{4} = 10, \tag{28}$$

$$d = 6 \Rightarrow y = \frac{36 - 36}{12} = 0, z = \frac{36 + 36}{12} = 6.$$

Other divisors of a , such as $d = 3$, yield:

$$y = \frac{36 - 9}{6} = 4.5 \notin \mathbb{N}, \tag{29}$$

which is not admissible. Therefore, only $d \in E(\sqrt{a})$ preserve integrality.

Moreover, note that for a fixed (a, y, z) , $d = z - y$ is the only possible positive value that satisfies the system:

$$\begin{cases} d^2 + 2yd - a = 0, \\ d^2 - 2zd + a = 0, \end{cases} \tag{30}$$

which has a unique solution $d = z - y > 0$ with $d \leq \sqrt{a}$. This confirms both the existence and uniqueness of d .

As already expressed in (23), the equation $a = d^2 + 2dy$ highlights the relationship between a , d , and y . This formulation shows that, for each fixed $d \in \mathbb{N}$, there exists a corresponding value of a such that the equation $a + y^2 = z^2$ admits a solution. For instance, for $d = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, we obtain:

$$a = 1 + 2y < 4 + 4y < 9 + 6y < \dots, \tag{31}$$

and for fixed values of $y = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, the values of a are

$$3 < 8 < 17 < \dots, 5 < 12 < 21 < \dots, 7 < 16 < 27 < \dots, \tag{32}$$

Combining these values yields a growing collection of integers:

$$a = 3, 5, 7, 8, 12, 16, 17, 21, 27, \dots, \tag{33}$$

which illustrates that the values of $a \in \mathbb{N}$ for which the equation has nontrivial solutions form a dense subset of the natural numbers. Although some integers such as

$a = 9, 11, 13, 15, 19, 20, 23, 25, \dots$ are not included in the examples above, these values do appear for larger combinations of d and y . This reinforces the idea that the set of admissible values of a is rich, increasingly populated, and densely distributed in \mathbb{N} as the parameters grow. This constructive viewpoint complements the structural result of Theorem 5 and highlights the abundance of admissible values of a .

We note that using (3), finding non-negative integers m, n, p , and q such that x and y are two predetermined positive integers can be quite laborious. To find all Pythagorean quadruples involving two predetermined positive integers x and y , we can introduce the following theorem.

Theorem 6. *Let x, y be two positive integers, and let $x^2 + y^2 = a \neq 2k$, where $k \geq 1$ is odd. The quadruple (x, y, z, w) is a Pythagorean quadruple if and only if there exists a unique $d \in E(\sqrt{a})$ such that*

$$x = x, y = y, z = \frac{a}{2d} - \frac{d}{2}, w = \frac{a}{2d} + \frac{d}{2}. \tag{34}$$

Proof 2. In Theorem 5, it suffices to consider $a = x^2 + y^2$ for all integers x and y such that $a \neq 2k$, where $k \geq 1$ is odd. Moreover, we observe that

$$x^2 + y^2 + \left(\frac{x^2 + y^2}{2d} - \frac{d}{2}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{x^2 + y^2}{2d} + \frac{d}{2}\right)^2, \tag{35}$$

holds for all x, y and for each d . In particular, if $a \in \mathbb{N}$ and $d \in E(\sqrt{a})$, then we obtain all $z, w \in \mathbb{N}$ satisfying all Pythagorean quadruples $x^2 + y^2 + z^2 = w^2$ for each predetermined value of a . \square

Using this method, we can reduce the problem of finding a Pythagorean quadruple that involves two predetermined positive integers x and y to the Diophantine equation $a + y^2 = z^2$.

More generally, let (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) be a Pythagorean n -tuple of integers. To find all Pythagorean n -tuple involving $n-2$ predetermined positive integers, a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{n-2} , the following theorem holds.

Theorem 7. *Let a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{n-2} be $n-2$ positive integers, and let $a_1^2 + a_2^2 + \dots + a_{n-2}^2 = a \neq 2k$, where $k \geq 1$ is odd. The n -tuple (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) is a Pythagorean n -tuple if and only if there exists a unique $d \in E(\sqrt{a})$ such that*

$$a_1 = a_1, a_2 = a_2, \dots, a_{n-2} = a_{n-2}, a_{n-1} = \frac{a}{2d} - \frac{d}{2}, \tag{36}$$

$$a_n = \frac{a}{2d} + \frac{d}{2}.$$

Proof 3. In Theorem 5, as in the previous proof, it suffices to consider $a = a_1^2 + a_2^2 + \dots + a_{n-2}^2$ for all integers a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{n-2} such that $a \neq 2k$, where $k \geq 1$ is odd. \square

The discovery of the parameterization and relationships among Diophantine equations of the form $a + y^2 = z^2$, as well as among Pythagorean n -tuples, highlights the fundamental role of d , belonging to a suitable class of divisors, in characterizing these results.

Having established a full characterization of Diophantine equations and n -tuples, the next natural step is to examine their algebraic properties and structural relationships. We now investigate the algebraic properties that naturally arise from these sets, with a particular focus on defining commutative monoids and groups.

3.2. Algebraic Structures. Now, we aim to study if the set of all Diophantine equations $a + y^2 = z^2$ forms a commutative infinite monoid. For this purpose, let us define the set

$T = \{(a, y, z) \text{ with } a, y, z \in \mathbb{N}, a \neq 0, \text{ such that } a + y^2 = z^2, a \neq 2k \text{ and } k \geq 1 \text{ is odd}\}$. We will prove the following theorem.

Theorem 8. *The set T together with the binary operation $f: T \times T \rightarrow T$, defined for all (a, y, z) and $(b, t, w) \in T$, such that*

$$(a, y, z) \cdot (b, t, w) = (ab, zt + yw, zt + yw + d_1 d_2) = (ab, zt + yw, zw + yt), \tag{37}$$

with $z - y = d_1 \in E(\sqrt{a})$ and $w - t = d_2 \in E(\sqrt{b})$, is a commutative infinite monoid with elements in \mathbb{N} .

Proof 4. The definition of the operation f implies that it is commutative. \square

The fact that f is a binary operation is deduced from Theorem 4. Indeed, the same proof holds replacing the Pythagorean triples with the Diophantine equations (a, y, z) , (b, t, w) , and (ab, r, s) , which are generated, respectively, by a, b , and ab using (15), with $d_1 \in E(\sqrt{a})$, $d_2 \in E(\sqrt{b})$, and $d_3 \in E(\sqrt{ab})$. However, directly we can prove that the $(ab, zt + yw, zw + yt) \in T$. We need to verify the following identity

$$ab + (zt + yw)^2 = (zw + yt)^2, \tag{38}$$

from which, we have

$$ab = z^2 w^2 + y^2 t^2 - z^2 t^2 - y^2 w^2, \tag{39}$$

that is

$$ab = (w^2 - t^2)(z^2 - y^2), \tag{40}$$

which is an identity. As a result, the operation (37) is a binary operation in T .

To prove that f is associative, for all (a, y, z) , (b, t, w) , and $(c, r, s) \in T$ with $d_1 \in E(\sqrt{a})$, $d_2 \in E(\sqrt{b})$, and $d_3 \in E(\sqrt{c})$, we verify that

$$[(a, y, z) \cdot (b, t, w)] \cdot (c, r, s) = (a, y, z) \cdot [(b, t, w) \cdot (c, r, s)]. \tag{41}$$

Using the operation (37) within the square brackets, we get

$$(ab, zt + yw, zt + yw + d_1d_2) \cdot (c, r, s) = (a, y, z) \cdot (bc, wr + ts, wr + ts + d_2d_3), \tag{42}$$

and reapplying it, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} &(abc, (zt + yw + d_1d_2)r + s(zt + yw), (zt + yw + d_1d_2)r + s(zt + yw) + d_1d_2d_3) \\ &= (abc, z(wr + ts) + y(wr + ts + d_2d_3), z(wr + ts) + y(wr + ts + d_2d_3) + d_1d_2d_3). \end{aligned} \tag{43}$$

To prove that the latter equation is an identity, it suffices to verify that

$$(zt + yw + d_1d_2)r + s(zt + yw) = z(wr + ts) + y(wr + ts + d_2d_3). \tag{44}$$

To this aim, by replacing $d_1 = z - y$, $d_2 = w - t$, and $d_3 = s - r$, we have

$$zwr + ytr + szt + syw = zwr + zts + yws + ytr, \tag{45}$$

that is an identity.

At last, we define the identity element as $(1, 0, 1)$ that obviously belongs to T . We also verify that, for all $(a, y, z) \in T$, we have

$$(a, y, z) \cdot (1, 0, 1) = (1, 0, 1) \cdot (a, y, z) = (a, y, z). \tag{46}$$

Using the operation (37) on both sides of above equation, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} &(a1, z0 + y1, z0 + y1 + (z - y)1) \\ &= (1a, 1y + 0z, 1y + 0z + 1(z - y)), \end{aligned} \tag{47}$$

that is,

$$(a, y, z) = (a, y, z). \tag{48}$$

Consequently, Theorem 8 is proved.

Example 1. Let us consider the Diophantine equations $a + y^2 = z^2$

$$(3, 1, 2), (5, 2, 3) \text{ and } (8, 1, 3) \in T, \tag{49}$$

since $3 + 1^2 = 4 = 2^2$, $5 + 2^2 = 9 = 3^2$, and $8 + 1^2 = 9 = 3^2$. We apply the binary operation f , defined in (37), to the pairs $(3, 1, 2)$, $(5, 2, 3)$, and $(5, 2, 3)$, $(8, 1, 3)$, obtaining, respectively,

$$\begin{aligned} &(3, 1, 2) \cdot (5, 2, 3) = (15, 7, 8) \in T \text{ and } (5, 2, 3) \cdot (8, 1, 3) \\ &= (40, 9, 11) \in T, \end{aligned} \tag{50}$$

since $15 + 7^2 = 64 = 8^2$ and $40 + 9^2 = 121 = 11^2$. Next, we apply the binary operation f again to the pairs $(15, 7, 8)$, $(8, 1, 3)$, and $(3, 1, 2)$, $(40, 9, 11)$, obtaining, respectively,

$$\begin{aligned} &(15, 7, 8) \cdot (8, 1, 3) = (120, 29, 31) \in T \text{ and } (3, 1, 2) \\ &\cdot (40, 9, 11) = (120, 29, 31) \in T, \end{aligned} \tag{51}$$

since $120 + 29^2 = 961 = 31^2$. By computing the previous operations, we have

$$[(3, 1, 2) \cdot (5, 2, 3)] \cdot (8, 1, 3) = (3, 1, 2) \cdot [(5, 2, 3) \cdot (8, 1, 3)], \tag{52}$$

which shows that the operation f is associative.

Let us observe that there is also another proof of same theorem. To prove that f is associative, for all $(y, z), (t, w) \in \mathbb{N}^2$, we define the operation:

$$(y, z) \otimes_1 (t, w) = (zt + yw, zw + yt), \tag{53}$$

and use the matrix notation in which (y, z) is represented by $\begin{pmatrix} z & y \\ y & z \end{pmatrix}$. Let us denote $N_1(y, z) = \det \begin{pmatrix} z & y \\ y & z \end{pmatrix}$. Then, the operation \otimes_1 is just usual matrix multiplication.

Indeed, we have

$$\begin{aligned} (y, z) \otimes_1 (t, w) &= \begin{pmatrix} z & y \\ y & z \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} w & t \\ t & w \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} zw + yt & zt + yw \\ zt + yw & zw + yt \end{pmatrix}. \end{aligned} \tag{54}$$

Now, the operation (37) can be written as follows

$$(a, y, z) \cdot (b, t, w) = (ab, (y, z) \otimes_1 (t, w)). \tag{55}$$

The first component of the result depends only on the first components a, b , while the second and third components of the result depend only on the second and the third components of the multiplied triplets.

Associativity is just a consequence of associativity of the matrix multiplication.

The identity matrix $(0, 1)$ is the neutral element corresponding to the identity element $(1, 0, 1)$.

Moreover, the conditions $a + y^2 = z^2$ and $b + t^2 = w^2$ can be interpreted as $a = N_1(y, z)$ and $b = N_1(t, w)$. Therefore, we have

$$a \cdot b = N_1(y, z) \cdot N_1(t, w) = N_1((y, z) \otimes_1 (t, w)). \tag{56}$$

This shows that the result of multiplying two elements from T also belongs to T . Thus, f is a binary operation, as established earlier.

It is also noteworthy that this previously obtained result can be retrieved through the second formula of Pythagorean triples provided in Theorem 4.

In the set of Pythagorean quadruples, we can also introduce a binary operation. Let us define the set

$$Q = \{(a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) \in \mathbb{Z} \text{ such that } a_1^2 + a_2^2 + a_3^2 = a_4^2 \text{ and } 0 < a_1^2 + a_2^2 = a \neq 2k, \text{ where } k \geq 1 \text{ is odd}\}, \quad (57)$$

and prove the following theorem.

Theorem 9. *The set Q together with the binary operation $g: Q \times Q \rightarrow Q$, defined for all (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) and $(b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4) \in Q$, such that*

$$\begin{aligned} &(a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) \cdot (b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4) \\ &= (a_1b_2 + a_2b_1, a_2b_2 - a_1b_1, a_4b_3 + a_3b_4, a_4b_4 + a_3b_3), \end{aligned} \quad (58)$$

is a commutative infinite monoid with elements in \mathbb{Z} .

Proof 5. The definition of the operation g implies that it is commutative. \square

To prove that the tuple $(a_1b_2 + a_2b_1, a_2b_2 - a_1b_1, a_4b_3 + a_3b_4, a_4b_4 + a_3b_3) \in Q$, we need to verify the following identity

$$\begin{aligned} &(a_1b_2 + a_2b_1)^2 + (a_2b_2 - a_1b_1)^2 + (a_4b_3 + a_3b_4)^2 \\ &= (a_4b_4 + a_3b_3)^2, \end{aligned} \quad (59)$$

from which, we have

$$a_1^2b_2^2 + a_2^2b_1^2 + a_2^2b_2^2 + a_1^2b_1^2 = a_4^2b_4^2 + a_3^2b_3^2 - a_4^2b_3^2 - a_3^2b_4^2, \quad (60)$$

that is

$$(a_3, a_4) \otimes_1 (b_3, b_4) = \begin{pmatrix} a_4 & a_3 \\ a_3 & a_4 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} b_4 & b_3 \\ b_3 & b_4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a_4b_4 + a_3b_3 & a_4b_3 + a_3b_4 \\ a_4b_3 + a_3b_4 & a_4b_4 + a_3b_3 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (66)$$

and

$$(a_1, a_2) \otimes_2 (b_1, b_2) = \begin{pmatrix} a_2 & a_1 \\ -a_1 & a_2 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} b_2 & b_1 \\ -b_1 & b_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a_2b_2 - a_1b_1 & a_1b_2 + a_2b_1 \\ -a_1b_2 - a_2b_1 & a_2b_2 - a_1b_1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (67)$$

Both operations \otimes_1 and \otimes_2 have the same identity matrix

$$(0, 1) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (68)$$

$$(a_1^2 + a_2^2)(b_1^2 + b_2^2) = (a_4^2 - a_3^2)(b_4^2 - b_3^2), \quad (61)$$

which is an identity. As a result, the operation (58) is a binary operation in Q .

To prove that g is associative, for all $(a_3, a_4), (b_3, b_4) \in \mathbb{N}^2$, we define

$$(a_3, a_4) \otimes_1 (b_3, b_4) = (a_4b_3 + a_3b_4, a_4b_4 + a_3b_3), \quad (62)$$

and use the matrix notation where (a_3, a_4) is represented by

$\begin{pmatrix} a_4 & a_3 \\ a_3 & a_4 \end{pmatrix}$. Let us denote

$$N_1(a_3, a_4) = \det \begin{pmatrix} a_4 & a_3 \\ a_3 & a_4 \end{pmatrix} = a_4^2 - a_3^2. \quad (63)$$

In the same way, for all $(a_1, a_2), (b_1, b_2) \in \mathbb{N}^2$, we define

$$(a_1, a_2) \otimes_2 (b_1, b_2) = (a_1b_2 + a_2b_1, a_2b_2 - a_1b_1), \quad (64)$$

and use the matrix notation where (a_1, a_2) is represented by

$\begin{pmatrix} a_2 & a_1 \\ -a_1 & a_2 \end{pmatrix}$. Let us denote

$$N_2(a_1, a_2) = \det \begin{pmatrix} a_2 & a_1 \\ -a_1 & a_2 \end{pmatrix} = a_2^2 + a_1^2. \quad (65)$$

The operations \otimes_1 and \otimes_2 are usual matrix multiplications, given, respectively, by

Now, the operation (58) can be written as follows

$$(a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) \cdot (b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4) = ((a_1, a_2) \otimes_2 (b_1, b_2), (a_3, a_4) \otimes_1 (b_3, b_4)). \tag{69}$$

Hence, for (62) and (64), associativity is a consequence of associativity of the matrix multiplication.

For (63) and (65), the assumption $a_1^2 + a_2^2 + a_3^2 = a_4^2$ can be written as $N_2(a_1, a_2) = N_1(a_3, a_4)$. This implies that Q is closed under multiplication, meaning that the product of any two elements from Q belongs to Q . Thus, g is a binary operation, as established earlier.

Moreover, by combination of neutral elements for \otimes_2 and \otimes_1 , we get the neutral quadruple $(0, 1, 0, 1)$.

Consequently, Theorem 9 is proved.

Example 2. Let us consider the Pythagorean quadruples $a_1^2 + a_2^2 + a_3^2 = a_4^2$

$$(2, -3, 6, 7), (1, 2, 2, 3), \text{ and } (-3, 4, 12, -13) \in Q, \tag{70}$$

since $2^2 + (-3)^2 + 6^2 = 49 = 7^2$, $1^2 + 2^2 + 2^2 = 9 = 3^2$ and $(-3)^2 + 4^2 + 12^2 = 169 = (-13)^2$. We apply the binary operation g , defined in (58), to the pairs $(2, -3, 6, 7)$, $(1, 2, 2, 3)$, and $(-3, 4, 12, -13)$, obtaining, respectively,

$$(2, -3, 6, 7) \cdot (1, 2, 2, 3) = (1, -8, 32, 33) \in Q \text{ and } (1, 2, 2, 3) \cdot (-3, 4, 12, -13) = (-2, 11, 10, -15) \in Q, \tag{71}$$

since $1^2 + (-8)^2 + 32^2 = 1089 = 33^2$ and $(-2)^2 + 11^2 + 10^2 = 225 = (-15)^2$. Next, we apply the binary operation g again to the pairs $(1, -8, 32, 33)$, $(-3, 4, 12, -13)$ and $(2, -3, 6, 7)$, $(-2, 11, 10, -15)$, obtaining, respectively,

$$(1, -8, 32, 33) \cdot (-3, 4, 12, -13) = (28, -29, -20, -45) \in Q, \tag{72}$$

and

$$(2, -3, 6, 7) \cdot (-2, 11, 10, -15) = (28, -29, -20, -45) \in Q, \tag{73}$$

since $28^2 + (-29)^2 + (-20)^2 = 2025 = (-45)^2$. By computing the previous operations, we have

$$[(2, -3, 6, 7) \cdot (1, 2, 2, 3)] \cdot (-3, 4, 12, -13) = (2, -3, 6, 7) \cdot [(1, 2, 2, 3) \cdot (-3, 4, 12, -13)], \tag{74}$$

which shows that the operation g is associative.

In the set of Pythagorean quadruples, if we want to find a monoid with elements in \mathbb{N} , we need to modify the binary operation and the proof. Let us define the set

$$F = \{(a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) \in \mathbb{N} \text{ such that } a_1^2 + a_2^2 + a_3^2 = a_4^2 \text{ and } 0 < a_1^2 + a_2^2 = a \neq 2k, \text{ where } k \geq 1 \text{ is odd}\}, \tag{75}$$

and prove the following theorem.

Theorem 10. *The set F together with the binary operation $s: F \times F \rightarrow F$, defined for all (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) and $(b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4) \in F$, such that*

$$(a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) \cdot (b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4) = (|a_1 b_2 + a_2 b_1|, |a_2 b_2 - a_1 b_1|, a_4 b_3 + a_3 b_4, a_4 b_3 + a_3 b_4 + d_1 d_2), \tag{76}$$

with $a_4 - a_3 = d_1 \in E(\sqrt{a})$ and $b_4 - b_3 = d_2 \in E(\sqrt{b})$, is a commutative infinite monoid with elements in \mathbb{N} .

Proof 6. To prove that the tuple $(|a_1b_2 + a_2b_1|, |a_2b_2 - a_1b_1|, a_4b_3 + a_3b_4, a_4b_3 + a_3b_4 + d_1d_2) \in F$, we need to verify the following identity

$$\begin{aligned} & |a_1b_2 + a_2b_1|^2 + |a_2b_2 - a_1b_1|^2 + (a_4b_3 + a_3b_4)^2 \\ &= (a_4b_3 + a_3b_4 + d_1d_2)^2, \end{aligned} \quad (77)$$

from which, we have

$$a_1^2b_2^2 + a_2^2b_1^2 + a_2^2b_2^2 + a_1^2b_1^2 = d_1^2d_2^2 + 2d_1d_2(a_3b_4 + a_4b_3). \quad (78)$$

This leads us to

$$\begin{aligned} & b_2^2(a_1^2 + a_2^2) + b_1^2(a_1^2 + a_2^2) \\ &= (a_4 - a_3)(b_4 - b_3)[a_4(b_3 + b_4) + a_3(b_3 + b_4)], \end{aligned} \quad (79)$$

from which it follows that

$$(a_1^2 + a_2^2)(b_1^2 + b_2^2) = (a_4^2 - a_3^2)(b_4^2 - b_3^2), \quad (80)$$

which is an identity. As a result, the operation (76) is a binary operation in F .

The definition of the operation s implies that it is commutative.

Next, we prove that the operation s is associative. For all (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) , (b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4) , and $(c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4) \in F$ where $a_4 - a_3 = d_1 \in E(\sqrt{a})$, $b_4 - b_3 = d_2 \in E(\sqrt{b})$, and $c_4 - c_3 = d_3 \in E(\sqrt{c})$, we verify

$$\begin{aligned} & [(a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) \cdot (b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4)] \cdot (c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4) \\ &= (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) \cdot [(b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4) \cdot (c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4)]. \end{aligned} \quad (81)$$

Using the operation (76) within the square brackets, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & (|a_1b_2 + a_2b_1|, |a_2b_2 - a_1b_1|, a_4b_3 + a_3b_4, a_4b_3 + a_3b_4 + d_1d_2) \cdot (c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4) \\ &= (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) \cdot (|b_1c_2 + b_2c_1|, |b_2c_2 - b_1c_1|, b_4c_3 + b_3c_4, b_4c_3 + b_3c_4 + d_2d_3), \end{aligned} \quad (82)$$

and reapplying it, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\left| |a_1b_2 + a_2b_1|c_2 + |a_2b_2 - a_1b_1|c_1 \right|, \left| |a_2b_2 - a_1b_1|c_2 - |a_1b_2 + a_2b_1|c_1 \right|, \right. \\ & (a_4b_3 + a_3b_4)c_4 + (a_4b_3 + a_3b_4 + d_1d_2)c_3, (a_4b_3 + a_3b_4)c_4 + (a_4b_3 + a_3b_4 + d_1d_2)c_3 + d_1d_2d_3 \left. \right), \\ &= \left(\left| |a_1|b_2c_2 - b_1c_1| + a_2|b_1c_2 + b_2c_1| \right|, \left| |a_2|b_2c_2 - b_1c_1| - a_1|b_1c_2 + b_2c_1| \right| \right. \\ & \left. a_3(b_4c_3 + b_3c_4 + d_2d_3) + a_4(b_4c_3 + b_3c_4), a_3(b_4c_3 + b_3c_4 + d_2d_3) + a_4(b_4c_3 + b_3c_4) + d_1d_2d_3 \right). \end{aligned} \quad (83)$$

Since $a_1b_2 + a_2b_1, b_1c_2 + b_2c_1, a_1, a_2, c_1$, and c_2 are positive, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\left| |a_1b_2c_2 + a_2b_1c_2 + |a_2b_2 - a_1b_1|c_1| \right|, \left| |a_2b_2 - a_1b_1|c_2 - a_1b_2c_1 - a_2b_1c_1| \right|, \right. \\ & (a_4b_3 + a_3b_4)c_4 + (a_4b_3 + a_3b_4 + d_1d_2)c_3, (a_4b_3 + a_3b_4)c_4 + (a_4b_3 + a_3b_4 + d_1d_2)c_3 + d_1d_2d_3 \left. \right), \\ &= \left(\left| |a_1|b_2c_2 - b_1c_1| + a_2b_1c_2 + a_2b_2c_1 \right|, \left| |a_2|b_2c_2 - b_1c_1| - a_1b_1c_2 - a_1b_2c_1| \right| \right. \\ & \left. a_3(b_4c_3 + b_3c_4 + d_2d_3) + a_4(b_4c_3 + b_3c_4), a_3(b_4c_3 + b_3c_4 + d_2d_3) + a_4(b_4c_3 + b_3c_4) + d_1d_2d_3 \right). \end{aligned} \quad (84)$$

It is easy to verify that, for each expression involving the values of $|a_2b_2 - a_1b_1|$ and $|b_2c_2 - b_1c_1|$, we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \left| a_1 b_2 c_2 + a_2 b_1 c_2 + |a_2 b_2 - a_1 b_1| c_1 \right| &= \left| a_1 |b_2 c_2 - b_1 c_1| + a_2 b_1 c_2 + a_2 b_2 c_1 \right|, \\ \left| a_2 b_2 - a_1 b_1 |c_2 - a_1 b_2 c_1 - a_2 b_1 c_1 \right| &= \left| a_2 |b_2 c_2 - b_1 c_1| - a_1 b_1 c_2 - a_1 b_2 c_1 \right|, \end{aligned} \tag{85}$$

hold. We note that, in order to have an identity in (85), we have set $|a_1 b_2 + a_2 b_1|$ in the definition of the binary operation s in (76), even though $a_1 b_2 + a_2 b_1$ is positive.

In conclusion, it suffices to verify that

$$(a_4 b_3 + a_3 b_4) c_4 + (a_4 b_3 + a_3 b_4 + d_1 d_2) c_3 = a_3 (b_4 c_3 + b_3 c_4 + d_2 d_3) + a_4 (b_4 c_3 + b_3 c_4), \tag{86}$$

that is

$$\begin{aligned} a_3 b_4 c_4 + a_4 b_3 c_3 + c_3 (a_4 - a_3) (b_4 - b_3) \\ = a_3 b_3 c_4 + a_4 b_4 c_3 + a_3 (b_4 - b_3) (c_4 - c_3), \end{aligned} \tag{87}$$

from which it is easy to prove that it is an identity.

Now, we define the identity element as $(0, 1, 0, 1)$, which obviously belongs to F . We also verify that, for all $(a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) \in F$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) \cdot (0, 1, 0, 1) &= (0, 1, 0, 1) \cdot (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) \\ &= (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4), \end{aligned} \tag{88}$$

Using the operation (76) on both sides of Equation (88), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} (|a_1 1 + a_2 0|, |a_2 1 - a_1 0|, a_4 0 + a_3 1, a_4 0 + a_3 1 + (a_4 - a_3) 1) \\ = (|0 a_2 + 1 a_1|, |1 a_2 - 0 a_1|, 1 a_3 + 0 a_4, 1 a_3 + 0 a_4 + 1 (a_4 - a_3)), \end{aligned} \tag{89}$$

which simplifies to

$$(a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) = (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4). \tag{90}$$

Consequently, Theorem 10 is proved.

Now, we aim to study whether the set of all Pythagorean quadruples forms a commutative infinite group. To achieve this goal, let us define the set

$D = \{ (a_1/a_4, (a_2/a_4), a_3/a_4), a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4 \in \mathbb{Z}, a_4 \neq 0, \text{ such that } a_1^2 + a_2^2 + a_3^2 = a_4^2 \text{ and } 0 < a_1^2 + a_2^2 = a \neq 2k, \text{ where } k \geq 1 \text{ is odd,} \}$ and prove the following theorem.

Theorem 11. *The set D together with the binary operation $l: D \times D \rightarrow D$, defined for all $(a_1/a_4, (a_2/a_4), a_3/a_4)$ and $(b_1/b_4, (b_2/b_4), b_3/b_4) \in D$, such that*

$$\begin{cases} l \left[\left(\frac{a_1}{a_4}, \frac{a_2}{a_4}, \frac{a_3}{a_4} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{b_1}{b_4}, \frac{b_2}{b_4}, \frac{b_3}{b_4} \right) \right] = \left(\frac{a_1 b_2 + a_2 b_1}{a_4 b_4 + a_3 b_3}, \frac{a_2 b_2 - a_1 b_1}{a_4 b_4 + a_3 b_3}, \frac{a_4 b_3 + a_3 b_4}{a_4 b_4 + a_3 b_3} \right), \\ \left(\frac{0}{a_1^2 + a_2^2}, \frac{a_1^2 + a_2^2}{a_1^2 + a_2^2}, \frac{0}{a_1^2 + a_2^2} \right) = \left(\frac{0}{1}, \frac{1}{1}, \frac{0}{1} \right), \\ \left(\frac{(a_1^2 + a_2^2)^n (a_1 b_2 + a_2 b_1)}{(a_1^2 + a_2^2)^n (a_4 b_4 + a_3 b_3)}, \frac{(a_1^2 + a_2^2)^n (a_2 b_2 - a_1 b_1)}{(a_1^2 + a_2^2)^n (a_4 b_4 + a_3 b_3)}, \frac{(a_1^2 + a_2^2)^n (a_4 b_3 + a_3 b_4)}{(a_1^2 + a_2^2)^n (a_4 b_4 + a_3 b_3)} \right) \\ = \left(\frac{a_1 b_2 + a_2 b_1}{a_4 b_4 + a_3 b_3}, \frac{a_2 b_2 - a_1 b_1}{a_4 b_4 + a_3 b_3}, \frac{a_4 b_3 + a_3 b_4}{a_4 b_4 + a_3 b_3} \right), \text{ for all } n \in \mathbb{N}, \end{cases} \tag{91}$$

is a commutative infinite group with elements in \mathbb{Q} .

Proof 7. We prove that in D , together with the binary operation (91) defined on D , the three group axioms hold, and the binary operation is commutative. \square

Firstly, we verify that the operation (91) is a binary operation on D , that is,

$$\begin{aligned} (a_1 b_2 + a_2 b_1)^2 + (a_2 b_2 - a_1 b_1)^2 + (a_4 b_3 + a_3 b_4)^2 \\ = (a_4 b_4 + a_3 b_3)^2. \end{aligned} \tag{92}$$

Since $a_4b_4 + a_3b_3 = a_4b_3 + a_3b_4 + d_1d_2$, Equation (92) is Equation (77), already verified to be an identity.

The definition of the operation l implies that it is commutative.

To prove the second axiom, we define the identity element as $(0/1, 1/1, 0/1)$.

Obviously, $(0/1, 1/1, 0/1) \in D$. Let us now verify that, for all $(a_1/a_4, a_2/a_4, a_3/a_4) \in D$, the equation

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{a_1}{a_4}, \frac{a_2}{a_4}, \frac{a_3}{a_4}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{0}{1}, \frac{1}{1}, \frac{0}{1}\right) &= \left(\frac{0}{1}, \frac{1}{1}, \frac{0}{1}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{a_1}{a_4}, \frac{a_2}{a_4}, \frac{a_3}{a_4}\right) \\ &= \left(\frac{a_1}{a_4}, \frac{a_2}{a_4}, \frac{a_3}{a_4}\right), \end{aligned} \tag{93}$$

holds. By applying the first condition in the operation (23) to the first two members of Equation (93), we obtain

$$\left(\frac{a_1 1 + a_2 0}{a_4 1 + a_3 0}, \frac{a_2 1 - a_1 0}{a_4 1 + a_3 0}, \frac{a_4 0 + a_3 1}{a_4 1 + a_3 0}\right) = \left(\frac{0 a_2 + 1 a_1}{1 a_4 + 0 a_3}, \frac{1 a_2 - 0 a_1}{1 a_4 + 0 a_3}, \frac{1 a_3 + 0 a_4}{1 a_4 + 0 a_3}\right), \tag{94}$$

which simplifies to

$$\left(\frac{a_1}{a_4}, \frac{a_2}{a_4}, \frac{a_3}{a_4}\right) = \left(\frac{a_1}{a_4}, \frac{a_2}{a_4}, \frac{a_3}{a_4}\right). \tag{95}$$

Therefore, the second axiom is proved.

To check the validity of the third axiom, for all $(a_1/a_4, a_2/a_4, a_3/a_4) \in D$, we define the inverse element as $(-a_1/a_4, a_2/a_4, -a_3/a_4)$. Obviously, $(-a_1/a_4, a_2/a_4, -a_3/a_4) \in D$. Let us now verify that, for all $(a_1/a_4, a_2/a_4, a_3/a_4) \in D$, the equation

$$\left(\frac{a_1}{a_4}, \frac{a_2}{a_4}, \frac{a_3}{a_4}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{-a_1}{a_4}, \frac{a_2}{a_4}, \frac{-a_3}{a_4}\right) = \left(\frac{-a_1}{a_4}, \frac{a_2}{a_4}, \frac{-a_3}{a_4}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{a_1}{a_4}, \frac{a_2}{a_4}, \frac{a_3}{a_4}\right) = \left(\frac{0}{1}, \frac{1}{1}, \frac{0}{1}\right), \tag{96}$$

holds. By applying the first condition in the operation (91) on the first two members of Equation (96), we obtain

$$\left(\frac{a_1 a_2 - a_2 a_1}{a_4^2 - a_3^2}, \frac{a_2^2 + a_1^2}{a_4^2 - a_3^2}, \frac{-a_4 a_3 + a_3 a_4}{a_4^2 - a_3^2}\right) = \left(\frac{-a_1 a_2 + a_2 a_1}{a_4^2 - a_3^2}, \frac{a_2^2 + a_1^2}{a_4^2 - a_3^2}, \frac{a_4 a_3 - a_3 a_4}{a_4^2 - a_3^2}\right), \tag{97}$$

that is,

$$\left(\frac{0}{a_4^2 - a_3^2}, \frac{a_2^2 + a_1^2}{a_4^2 - a_3^2}, \frac{0}{a_4^2 - a_3^2}\right) = \left(\frac{0}{a_4^2 - a_3^2}, \frac{a_2^2 + a_1^2}{a_4^2 - a_3^2}, \frac{0}{a_4^2 - a_3^2}\right). \tag{98}$$

Since $a_4^2 - a_3^2 = a_2^2 + a_1^2$, according to the second condition in the operation (91), we obtain

$$\left(\frac{0}{1}, \frac{1}{1}, \frac{0}{1}\right) = \left(\frac{0}{1}, \frac{1}{1}, \frac{0}{1}\right), \tag{99}$$

and consequently, the third axiom is proved.

We observe that including the second condition in the operation (91) allows us to obtain the identity element. To avoid ambiguity, it also eliminates the possibility of getting elements of the form $(0/a_2^2 + a_1^2, a_2^2 + a_1^2/a_2^2 + a_1^2, 0/a_2^2 + a_1^2)$

such that $0^2 + (a_2^2 + a_1^2)^2 + 0^2 = (a_2^2 + a_1^2)^2$, for the same product. For these same reasons, whenever we have a product of elements in D that includes both $(a_1/a_4, a_2/a_4, a_3/a_4)$ and $(-a_1/a_4, a_2/a_4, (-a_3)/a_4)$, it is necessary to divide both the numerators and denominators of the fractions in the final result of the product by $a_1^2 + a_2^2$. Otherwise, for example, if we consider the product

$$\left(\frac{a_1}{a_4}, \frac{a_2}{a_4}, \frac{a_3}{a_4}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{b_1}{b_4}, \frac{b_2}{b_4}, \frac{b_3}{b_4}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{c_1}{c_4}, \frac{c_2}{c_4}, \frac{c_3}{c_4}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{-a_1}{a_4}, \frac{a_2}{a_4}, \frac{-a_3}{a_4}\right), \tag{100}$$

without dividing by $a_1^2 + a_2^2$, we would end up with elements of the form

$$\left(\frac{(a_1^2 + a_2^2)^2 (b_1 c_2 + b_2 c_1)}{(a_1^2 + a_2^2)^2 (b_4 c_4 + b_3 c_3)}, \frac{(a_1^2 + a_2^2)^2 (b_2 c_2 - b_1 c_1)}{(a_1^2 + a_2^2)^2 (b_4 c_4 + b_3 c_3)}, \frac{(a_1^2 + a_2^2)^2 (b_4 c_3 + b_3 c_4)}{(a_1^2 + a_2^2)^2 (b_4 c_4 + b_3 c_3)}\right), \tag{101}$$

such that

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[(a_1^2 + a_2^2)(b_1c_2 + b_2c_1) \right]^2 + \left[(a_1^2 + a_2^2)(b_2c_2 - b_1c_1) \right]^2 \\ & + \left[(a_1^2 + a_2^2)(b_4c_3 + b_3c_4) \right]^2 = \left[(a_1^2 + a_2^2)(b_4c_4 + b_3c_3) \right]^2. \end{aligned} \tag{102}$$

While dividing by $a_1^2 + a_2^2$, we obtain elements of the form

$$\left(\frac{b_1c_2 + b_2c_1}{b_4c_4 + b_3c_3}, \frac{b_2c_2 - b_1c_1}{b_4c_4 + b_3c_3}, \frac{b_4c_3 + b_3c_4}{b_4c_4 + b_3c_3} \right). \tag{103}$$

Such that

$$\begin{aligned} & (b_1c_2 + b_2c_1)^2 + (b_2c_2 - b_1c_1)^2 + (b_4c_3 + b_3c_4)^2 \\ & = (b_4c_4 + b_3c_3)^2. \end{aligned} \tag{104}$$

Therefore, the third condition eliminates the possibility of obtaining two results for the same product.

Let us notice that, using the commutative property for the same product, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\frac{a_1}{a_4}, \frac{a_2}{a_4}, \frac{a_3}{a_4} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{b_1}{b_4}, \frac{b_2}{b_4}, \frac{b_3}{b_4} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{c_1}{c_4}, \frac{c_2}{c_4}, \frac{c_3}{c_4} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{-a_1}{a_4}, \frac{a_2}{a_4}, \frac{-a_3}{a_4} \right) \\ & = \left(\frac{b_1}{b_4}, \frac{b_2}{b_4}, \frac{b_3}{b_4} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{c_1}{c_4}, \frac{c_2}{c_4}, \frac{c_3}{c_4} \right) \cdot \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \\ & = \left(\frac{b_1c_2 + b_2c_1}{b_4c_4 + b_3c_3}, \frac{b_2c_2 - b_1c_1}{b_4c_4 + b_3c_3}, \frac{b_4c_3 + b_3c_4}{b_4c_4 + b_3c_3} \right). \end{aligned} \tag{105}$$

In this case, we used the second condition in the operation (91). Clearly, if both elements $(a_1/a_4, a_2/a_4, a_3/a_4)$ and $(-a_1/a_4, a_2/a_4, -a_3/a_4)$ appear n times, it is necessary to divide by $(a_1^2 + a_2^2)^n$.

Therefore, the second and third conditions in operation (91) have been fully justified.

To prove the first axiom, we verify that the condition

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\left(\frac{a_1}{a_4}, \frac{a_2}{a_4}, \frac{a_3}{a_4} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{b_1}{b_4}, \frac{b_2}{b_4}, \frac{b_3}{b_4} \right) \right] \cdot \left(\frac{c_1}{c_4}, \frac{c_2}{c_4}, \frac{c_3}{c_4} \right) \\ & = \left(\frac{a_1}{a_4}, \frac{a_2}{a_4}, \frac{a_3}{a_4} \right) \cdot \left[\left(\frac{b_1}{b_4}, \frac{b_2}{b_4}, \frac{b_3}{b_4} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{c_1}{c_4}, \frac{c_2}{c_4}, \frac{c_3}{c_4} \right) \right], \end{aligned} \tag{106}$$

holds for all $(a_1/a_4, a_2/a_4, a_3/a_4)$, $(b_1/b_4, b_2/b_4, b_3/b_4)$, and $(c_1/c_4, c_2/c_4, c_3/c_4) \in D$ with

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\frac{b_1}{b_4}, \frac{b_2}{b_4}, \frac{b_3}{b_4} \right) \neq \left(\frac{-a_1}{a_4}, \frac{a_2}{a_4}, \frac{-a_3}{a_4} \right) \text{ and } \left(\frac{c_1}{c_4}, \frac{c_2}{c_4}, \frac{c_3}{c_4} \right) \\ & \neq \left(\frac{-b_1}{b_4}, \frac{b_2}{b_4}, \frac{-b_3}{b_4} \right). \end{aligned} \tag{107}$$

To this end, by first applying the first condition in the operation (91) to the terms within the square brackets in (106), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\frac{a_1b_2 + a_2b_1}{a_4b_4 + a_3b_3}, \frac{a_2b_2 - a_1b_1}{a_4b_4 + a_3b_3}, \frac{a_4b_3 + a_3b_4}{a_4b_4 + a_3b_3} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{c_1}{c_4}, \frac{c_2}{c_4}, \frac{c_3}{c_4} \right) \\ & = \left(\frac{a_1}{a_4}, \frac{a_2}{a_4}, \frac{a_3}{a_4} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{b_1c_2 + b_2c_1}{b_4c_4 + b_3c_3}, \frac{b_2c_2 - b_1c_1}{b_4c_4 + b_3c_3}, \frac{b_4c_3 + b_3c_4}{b_4c_4 + b_3c_3} \right). \end{aligned} \tag{108}$$

Reapplying the operation to the result, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\frac{(a_1b_2 + a_2b_1)c_2 + (a_2b_2 - a_1b_1)c_1}{(a_4b_4 + a_3b_3)c_4 + (a_4b_3 + a_3b_4)c_3}, \frac{(a_2b_2 - a_1b_1)c_2 - (a_1b_2 + a_2b_1)c_1}{(a_4b_4 + a_3b_3)c_4 + (a_4b_3 + a_3b_4)c_3}, \right. \\ & \left. \frac{(a_4b_4 + a_3b_3)c_3 + (a_4b_3 + a_3b_4)c_4}{(a_4b_4 + a_3b_3)c_4 + (a_4b_3 + a_3b_4)c_3} \right) = \left(\frac{(a_1b_2 + a_2b_1)c_2 + (a_2b_2 - a_1b_1)c_1}{(a_4(b_4c_4 + b_3c_3) + a_3(b_4c_3 + b_3c_4))}, \right. \\ & \left. \frac{a_2(b_2c_2 - b_1c_1) - a_1(b_1c_2 + b_2c_1)}{a_4(b_4c_4 + b_3c_3) + a_3(b_4c_3 + b_3c_4)}, \frac{a_4(b_4c_3 + b_3c_4) + a_3(b_4c_4 + b_3c_3)}{a_4(b_4c_4 + b_3c_3) + a_3(b_4c_3 + b_3c_4)} \right), \end{aligned} \tag{109}$$

which is easily verified to be an identity in \mathbb{Q} . Thus, the associativity condition (106) is satisfied.

On the other hand, if $(b_1/b_4, b_2/b_4, b_3/b_4) = (-a_1/a_4, a_2/a_4, -a_3/a_4)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\left(\frac{a_1}{a_4}, \frac{a_2}{a_4}, \frac{a_3}{a_4} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{-a_1}{a_4}, \frac{a_2}{a_4}, \frac{-a_3}{a_4} \right) \right] \cdot \left(\frac{c_1}{c_4}, \frac{c_2}{c_4}, \frac{c_3}{c_4} \right) \\ & = \left(\frac{a_1}{a_4}, \frac{a_2}{a_4}, \frac{a_3}{a_4} \right) \cdot \left[\left(\frac{-a_1}{a_4}, \frac{a_2}{a_4}, \frac{-a_3}{a_4} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{c_1}{c_4}, \frac{c_2}{c_4}, \frac{c_3}{c_4} \right) \right]. \end{aligned} \tag{110}$$

This simplifies to

$$\begin{aligned} & \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \left(\frac{c_1}{c_4}, \frac{c_2}{c_4}, \frac{c_3}{c_4} \right) \\ & = \left(\frac{a_1}{a_4}, \frac{a_2}{a_4}, \frac{a_3}{a_4} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{-a_1c_2 + a_2c_1}{a_4c_4 - a_3c_3}, \frac{a_2c_2 + a_1c_1}{a_4c_4 - a_3c_3}, \frac{a_4c_3 - a_3c_4}{a_4c_4 - a_3c_3} \right). \end{aligned} \tag{111}$$

Consequently, we obtain

$$\left(\frac{c_1}{c_4}, \frac{c_2}{c_4}, \frac{c_3}{c_4}\right) = \left(\frac{a_1(a_2c_2 + a_1c_1) + a_2(-a_1c_2 + a_2c_1)}{a_4(a_4c_4 - a_3c_3) + a_3(a_4c_3 - a_3c_4)}, \frac{a_2(a_2c_2 + a_1c_1) - a_1(-a_1c_2 + a_2c_1)}{a_4(a_4c_4 - a_3c_3) + a_3(a_4c_3 - a_3c_4)}, \frac{a_4(a_4c_3 - a_3c_4) + a_3(a_4c_4 - a_3c_3)}{a_4(a_4c_4 - a_3c_3) + a_3(a_4c_3 - a_3c_4)}\right), \tag{112}$$

from which

$$\left(\frac{c_1}{c_4}, \frac{c_2}{c_4}, \frac{c_3}{c_4}\right) = \left(\frac{(a_1^2 + a_2^2)c_1}{(a_4^2 - a_3^2)c_4}, \frac{(a_1^2 + a_2^2)c_2}{(a_4^2 - a_3^2)c_4}, \frac{(a_4^2 - a_3^2)c_3}{(a_4^2 - a_3^2)c_4}\right). \tag{113}$$

Moreover, since $a_4^2 - a_3^2 = a_1^2 + a_2^2$, we have

$$\left(\frac{c_1}{c_4}, \frac{c_2}{c_4}, \frac{c_3}{c_4}\right) = \left(\frac{(a_1^2 + a_2^2)c_1}{(a_1^2 + a_2^2)c_4}, \frac{(a_1^2 + a_2^2)c_2}{(a_1^2 + a_2^2)c_4}, \frac{(a_1^2 + a_2^2)c_3}{(a_1^2 + a_2^2)c_4}\right), \tag{114}$$

and, for the third condition in the operation (91), we obtain an identity even in the case $(b_1/b_4, b_2/b_4, b_3/b_4) = (-a_1/a_4, a_2/a_4, -a_3/a_4)$. Analogously, if $(c_1/c_4, c_2/c_4, c_3/c_4) = (-b_1/b_4, b_2/b_4, -b_3/b_4)$, the same conclusion holds. Therefore, the first axiom is established.

Consequently, Theorem 11 is proved.

Remark 2. The normalization by $a_1^2 + a_2^2$ in the group operation (91) is crucial for two reasons.

First, it ensures that the resulting element remains in reduced form and belongs to the same set D , defined by the constraint:

$$\left(\frac{a_1}{a_4}, \frac{a_2}{a_4}, \frac{a_3}{a_4}\right) \text{ with } a_1^2 + a_2^2 + a_3^2 = a_4^2. \tag{115}$$

$$\left(\frac{0}{5}, \frac{5}{5}, \frac{0}{5}\right) \text{ which corresponds to the quadruple } (0, 5, 0, 5) \neq (0, 1, 0, 1), \tag{118}$$

Taking into account the second condition in the operation (91), we obtain

$$\left(\frac{0}{5}, \frac{5}{5}, \frac{0}{5}\right) = \left(\frac{0}{1}, \frac{1}{1}, \frac{0}{1}\right) \text{ which corresponds to the quadruple } (0, 1, 0, 1), \tag{119}$$

and thus the identity element is recovered. When composing the same pair twice, the resulting components (both numerator and denominator) are scaled by:

$$(a_1^2 + a_2^2)^2 = 5^2 = 25. \tag{120}$$

Without the normalization, repeated operations between elements such as (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) and $(-a_1, a_2, -a_3, a_4)$ could yield inflated numerators and denominators, violating closure in D .

Second, the normalization guarantees that the binary operation is well defined and associative across all elements. In particular, it prevents ambiguity when both the element and its inverse appear n times as a pair in a composition, and ensures that the identity element is correctly restored.

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \text{ which corresponds to the quadruple } (0, 1, 0, 1). \tag{116}$$

This mechanism mirrors the classical normalization of rational points on the unit circle or the projective line, where scalar multiples must be reduced to preserve group properties.

Example 3. Consider two elements of D :

$$\left(\frac{1}{3}, \frac{2}{3}, \frac{2}{3}\right), \left(\frac{-1}{3}, \frac{2}{3}, \frac{-2}{3}\right), \tag{117}$$

these two elements are opposites and their product under the group operation should yield the identity. Applying the operation (91) once yields a quadruple whose components are scaled by $a_1^2 + a_2^2 = 1^2 + 2^2 = 5$, that is

This happens because the group operation involves summing terms like $a_1b_2 + a_2b_1$, and the repeated composition introduces the square of the original norm. Without dividing by this factor, the resulting quadruple would not be reduced and could fall outside the domain D . Thus, we normalize the result by dividing each component of the

resulting quadruple by $(a_1^2 + a_2^2)^2$, which ensures that we recover the identity element.

This illustrates the role of normalization: It guarantees that group operations preserve the canonical form of elements in D , avoid growth of components, and ensure closure of the structure and group identity in D .

Next, we introduce the following theorem.

Theorem 12. *The set of all Pythagorean quadruples is a commutative infinite group with elements in \mathbb{Z} .*

Proof 8. We define the set

$$A = \{(a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) \text{ with } a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4 \in \mathbb{Z}, a_4 \neq 0, \text{ such that } \left(\frac{a_1}{a_4}, \frac{a_2}{a_4}, \frac{a_3}{a_4}\right) \in D \text{ and } 0 < a_1^2 + a_2^2 = a \neq 2k, \text{ where } k \geq 1 \text{ is odd}\}. \quad (121)$$

That is the set of Pythagorean quadruples with elements in \mathbb{Z} . We also consider the function $h: A \rightarrow D$ such that

$$\begin{cases} h(a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) = \left(\frac{a_1}{a_4}, \frac{a_2}{a_4}, \frac{a_3}{a_4}\right), \\ h[(a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) \cdot (b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4)] = \left(\frac{a_1}{a_4}, \frac{a_2}{a_4}, \frac{a_3}{a_4}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{b_1}{b_4}, \frac{b_2}{b_4}, \frac{b_3}{b_4}\right), \\ = \left(\frac{a_1 b_2 + a_2 b_1}{a_4 b_4 + a_3 b_3}, \frac{a_2 b_2 - a_1 b_1}{a_4 b_4 + a_3 b_3}, \frac{a_4 b_3 + a_3 b_4}{a_4 b_4 + a_3 b_3}\right), \text{ for all } n \in \mathbb{N}. \end{cases} \quad (122)$$

Additionally, we introduce the function $j: D \rightarrow A$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} j\left(\frac{a_1 b_2 + a_2 b_1}{a_4 b_4 + a_3 b_3}, \frac{a_2 b_2 - a_1 b_1}{a_4 b_4 + a_3 b_3}, \frac{a_4 b_3 + a_3 b_4}{a_4 b_4 + a_3 b_3}\right) \\ = (a_1 b_2 + a_2 b_1, a_2 b_2 - a_1 b_1, a_4 b_3 + a_3 b_4, a_4 b_4 + a_3 b_3). \end{aligned} \quad (123)$$

We now define the composite function

$$m = j \circ h: A \rightarrow A, \quad (124)$$

such that

$$\begin{cases} m[(a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) \cdot (b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4)] = (a_1 b_2 + a_2 b_1, a_2 b_2 - a_1 b_1, a_4 b_3 + a_3 b_4, \\ a_4 b_4 + a_3 b_3), \text{ if } (b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4) \neq (-a_1, a_2, -a_3, a_4), \\ m[(a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) \cdot (-a_1, a_2, -a_3, a_4)] = (0, 1, 0, 1), \\ ((a_1^2 + a_2^2)^n (a_1 b_2 + a_2 b_1), (a_1^2 + a_2^2)^n (a_2 b_2 - a_1 b_1), (a_1^2 + a_2^2)^n (a_4 b_3 + a_3 b_4), \\ (a_1^2 + a_2^2)^n (a_4 b_4 + a_3 b_3)) = (a_1 b_2 + a_2 b_1, a_2 b_2 - a_1 b_1, a_4 b_3 + a_3 b_4, a_4 b_4 + a_3 b_3), \\ \text{for all } n \in \mathbb{N}, \end{cases} \quad (125)$$

which is a binary operation on A .

Obviously, the binary operation m is both associative and commutative, with the identity element $(0, 1, 0, 1)$ and the inverse element $(-a_1, a_2, -a_3, a_4)$. To avoid ambiguity, in

(125), we use $(0, 1, 0, 1)$ whenever $(b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4) = (-a_1, a_2, -a_3, a_4)$. For the same reason, if the triples (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) and $(-a_1, a_2, -a_3, a_4)$ appear n times, we set the third condition in (125).

Consequently, Theorem 12 is proved. \square

Example 4. Consider two elements $(2, -3, 6, 7)$ and $(1, 2, 2, 3) \in A$ such that $(2/7, (-3/7), 6/7)$ and $(1/3, 2/3, 22/3) \in D$, since $2^2 + (-3)^2 + 6^2 = 49 = 7^2$, and $1^2 + 2^2 + 2^2 = 9 = 3^2$. We apply the binary operation h , defined in (122), to the pairs $(2, -3, 6, 7)$, $(1, 2, 2, 3)$, obtaining

$$\begin{aligned} h[(2, -3, 6, 7) \cdot (1, 2, 2, 3)] &= \left(\frac{2}{7}, \frac{-3}{7}, \frac{6}{7}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{1}{3}, \frac{2}{3}, \frac{2}{3}\right) \\ &= \left(\frac{1}{33}, \frac{-8}{33}, \frac{32}{33}\right). \end{aligned} \quad (126)$$

Next, we apply the binary operation j , defined in (123), to the element $(1/33, -8/33, 32/33) \in D$, obtaining

$$j\left(\frac{1}{33}, \frac{-8}{33}, \frac{32}{33}\right) = (1, -8, 32, 33) \in A, \quad (127)$$

since $1^2 + (-8)^2 + 32^2 = 1089 = 33^2$. By computing the previous operations, we have

$$m[(2, -3, 6, 7) \cdot (1, 2, 2, 3)] = (1, -8, 32, 33), \quad (128)$$

which coincides with the result of the binary operation g , defined in (58). Thanks to the composite function m , we retrieve the inverse element (as previously seen in Example 2), confirming that the set A forms a commutative infinite group with elements in \mathbb{Z} .

In [16], it was shown that the commutative group of primitive Pythagorean triples with elements in \mathbb{Z} is a subgroup of the commutative group of all Pythagorean triples with elements in \mathbb{Z} .

We now present the following remark.

Remark 3. The set of primitive Pythagorean quadruples with elements in \mathbb{Z} does not constitute a subgroup of the group of all Pythagorean quadruples with elements in \mathbb{Z} .

Indeed, this can be demonstrated by noting that if we apply the operation (125) to the primitive Pythagorean quadruples $(2, 14, 49, 51)$ and $(-1, 2, 2, -3)$, the resulting Pythagorean quadruple $(-10, 30, -45, -55)$ is not primitive.

Every Pythagorean triple $x^2 + y^2 = z^2$ can be interpreted as a Diophantine equation $a + y^2 = z^2$ with x, y, z , and $a \in \mathbb{N}$. Observe that the binary operation in Corollary 1 is identical to the one defined in Theorem 8, and the identity element remains the same. Moreover, applying the binary operation f to the two Diophantine equations (a, y, z) and (a, t, w) results in a Pythagorean triple.

As a consequence, we have the following Corollary 3.

Corollary 3. *The monoid (M, r) , with elements in \mathbb{N} , is a submonoid of the monoid (T, f) .*

Furthermore, a Pythagorean triple (x, y, z) can be considered a Pythagorean quadruple in the form $(0, x, y, z)$. When the binary operation defined in Theorem 12 is applied to Pythagorean quadruples in the form $(0, x, y, z)$, it is equivalent to the binary operation in Corollary 1, with the

same identity element. Moreover, applying the binary operation m to the two Pythagorean quadruples (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) and (a_1, a_2, b_3, b_4) yields a Pythagorean triple. As a consequence, we have the following Corollary 4.

Corollary 4. *The group (M, i) is a subgroup of the group (A, m) .*

4. Conclusion and Remarks

Beyond the algebraic structures discussed in this paper, the results presented have natural implications for other mathematical fields. For instance, the explicit characterization of Pythagorean n -tuples can aid in studying integer lattice points on spheres in geometry, providing insights into sphere packings and integer distance problems. Additionally, the algebraic formulation of these structures offers potential applications in analytical number theory, especially in the study of quadratic forms, modular arithmetic, and in the context of solving congruences and residue class systems. These connections further highlight the relevance of the presented methods to a broader mathematical audience.

The study of algebraic structures such as monoids and groups within sets of Diophantine solutions is of growing interest in contemporary number theory. The generalization to n -tuples provides a comprehensive framework for studying relationships in higher dimensions. This approach has potential implications for algebraic topology and in the context of modern research in number theory and their applications, such as cryptography, offering tools for both theoretical exploration and practical computation. In cryptographic contexts, the existence of algebraic operations satisfying closure and associativity could inspire the design of primitives based on structured Diophantine sets, which may offer novel properties such as symmetry or composability under constraints. Their commutative and associative properties are particularly useful for algorithmic constructions and secure computation protocols.

A natural next step could involve studying the parameterizations of Pythagorean n -tuples, seeking a representation analogous to Theorem 3 and determining all primitive Pythagorean n -tuples with $n > 3$.

This method could also be applied to explore further relationships among Pythagorean n -tuples. For instance, it might facilitate the identification of a suitable binary operation on Pythagorean n -tuples with $n > 4$, enabling the definition of groups and monoids within the set of Pythagorean n -tuples. Such an approach could be utilized to investigate other problems, some of which remain open. In particular, it would be interesting to identify additional parameterizations, relationships, characterizations, and further groups or semigroups within the set of equations $a + y^2 = z^2$ and the set of Pythagorean n -tuples, which could potentially have applications in analytic number theory.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no datasets were generated during the current study.

Conflicts of Interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

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